

Multifractal Scaling in Cross-Sectoral Financial Markets: Connections with Diffusion and Chaos

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Abstract

Financial return series show deviations from Gaussian behaviour such as fat tails, volatility clustering, and long-range nonlinear dependence. Daily log-returns of 50 assets from six sectors such as large-cap technology, financials, healthcare and consumer, energy and industrials, commodities and cryptocurrencies, and international ETFs during the period from January 2010 to April 2026 are studied using the Multifractal Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (MF-DFA). Nonlinear generalised Hurst exponents and concave singularity spectra confirm ubiquitous multifractality in all assets, with pronounced cross-sectoral heterogeneity in the singularity spectrum width $\Delta\alpha$. Symmetric fluctuation analysis reveals systematic decrease in Pearson correlation between positive- and negative-order fluctuation functions at large moment orders, which implies that the extreme positive and negative fluctuations follow fundamentally different scaling laws. Cumulant-based characteristic function scaling identifies significant non-Gaussian tail structure in 43 of 50 assets, concentrated at horizons of 20 trading days or fewer. A geometric box-counting analysis of the empirical characteristic function path yields fractal dimensions increasing near-parabolically with moment order, consistent with scaling behaviour predicted for hydrodynamic modes in chaotic diffusive systems. Collectively, the findings establish sector-dependent market complexity and demonstrate that standard risk models predicated on return normality systematically underestimate tail risk across all examined asset classes.

Keywords: Multifractal analysis, Detrended fluctuation analysis, Singularity spectrum, Fat tails, Characteristic function.

1 Introduction

The standard model of financial returns, originating from Bachelier's random walk hypothesis [1] and the central motif within the efficient market hypothesis [2, 3], assumes that price changes are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d) [4] with finite variance. Under this framework, returns converge toward a Gaussian distribution as the observation horizon increases (seemingly following the Law of Large Numbers) , and the temporal structure of the series is characterized by a single scaling exponent, namely the Hurst exponent $H = 0.5$. This implies the absence of long-term memory and predictability in price dynamics.

These assumptions have been challenged by empirical results in the past. Financial return series have been known to exhibit fat-tailed distributions [5] with tail exponents $\gamma \approx 3$ [6, 7], volatility clustering [8, 9], and long-range dependence in volatility and higher-order moments [10]. Leverage effects have also been reported, and negative returns are found to magnify or even generate future volatility more strongly than positive returns of similar magnitude [11]. These features are the fundamental properties of financial markets across asset classes that thrive off of trader psychology and historical data.

A monofractal framework is thus at a disadvantage when it comes to capturing such empirical regularities [12]. A monofractal process has a constant global Hurst exponent, meaning that all statistical moments scale identically, and small and large fluctuations in the time series have the same temporal structure. This assumption is broken by financial return series whose scaling behaviour of fluctuations is dependent on the magnitude of fluctuations, implying heterogeneous dynamics across scales. Large fluctuations, which are often associated with market stress and extreme events, have fundamentally different scaling properties from small, regular fluctuations. Thus any model that assumes similarity between the varying range of fluctuations is inherently prone to bias at disastrous levels and is ballooned disproportionately by more predictions built on top of said predictions as seen in the derivatives market. This heterogeneous scaling behaviour has deeper roots in classical chaos which is intimately connected with fractal-like spectra [13] and the structure of correlation functions [14, 15].

Thus, multifractal analysis circumvents this limitation as a natural extension when it comes to solving this problem [16]. Instead of representing the dynamics of the system with a single exponent, it characterizes the full spectrum of local singularity strengths through the singularity spectrum [17, 18] and captures the dependence of scaling behaviour on the moment order q via the generalised Hurst exponent $H(q)$ [19]. A non-linear relation between $H(q)$ on q , coupled with a time-series dependent singularity spectrum, indicates the presence of complex multifractal structure. The width $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_{\max} - \alpha_{\min}$ is a stable measure of this heterogeneity, with larger values corresponding to increasingly

complicated heterogenous dynamics.

Mandelbrot was the first to use multifractal methods on financial time series [5]. He saw strong similarities between financial markets and turbulent systems [20, 21, 22, 23]. This discovery resulted in the creation of models such as the Multifractal Model of Asset Returns (MMAR) [24] and Markov-switching multifractal (MSM) models [25, 26, 27], along with various other cascade detection models that include hierarchical volatility structures. Empirical studies utilising techniques such as detrended fluctuation analysis, structure functions, and wavelet-based methods have validated the presence of multifractality across various financial assets, including foreign exchange, commodities, and interest rates. One of these methods that has been shown to work is Multifractal Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (MF-DFA) [28, 29]. This is because it can handle non-stationarities and polynomial trends, which are important parts of financial data.

Despite the extensive literature, systematic cross-sectoral comparisons across a heterogeneous asset universe remain relatively limited [30]. Majority of the existing studies shed light on a single asset class [31], which constrains the ability to draw general conclusions from sector-level variation in multifractal behaviour. This limitation is non-trivial, as the multifractal spectral width has been previously proposed as a proxy for market inefficiency [32, 33]: wider singularity spectra indicates complex heterogeneity in scaling behaviour, while narrower spectra indicate dynamics closer to monofractal behaviour.

This study aims to bridge this gap by conducting a comprehensive multifractal analysis of 50 assets spanning six economically distinct sectors—technology, financials, healthcare and consumer, energy and industrials, commodities and cryptocurrencies, and international ETFs—over the period January 2010 to April 2026, which addresses the need for cross-asset investigations highlighted in relevant literature [16]. The empirical results reveal pronounced cross-sectoral heterogeneity in multifractal structure as seen in other cross-market analysis research [34], with sectors such as healthcare and consumer exhibiting particularly wide singularity spectra, while others display comparatively moderate scaling complexity.

We also propose a symmetric fluctuation analysis by examining the Pearson correlation between the positive-order and negative-order fluctuation functions $F_{+q}(s)$ and $F_{-q}(s)$ as a function of $|q|$ [35, 36]. The observed decrease of correlation for large $|q|$ is evidence of asymmetry between large and small fluctuations, indicating that extreme events are controlled by different scaling mechanisms and dynamics than smaller fluctuations, as found in typical market microstructure [37]. Drawdown distributions analysis uncovers deviations from the behaviour expected under independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) returns, bringing to light unique regime-based price dynamics and also the fatal flaw that traditional return-based models have [38]. This is particularly concerning as models

trained on historic data cannot differentiate between the actual data distribution and the seemingly noisy distribution that is constituted by the drawdowns and other unnatural deviations. Coupling this with the build-up of strong correlation in the movements of related stocks leads to systemic shocks across financial markets which is often called as systemic risk as well in popular literature [38].

The crux of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 details the theoretical framework of multifractality, including the singularity spectrum, mass scaling exponents, and generalised Hurst exponents and their exclusive connections to financial theory. Section 3 highlights the MF-DFA methodology and other related parameters that help capture properties unique to each stock. Section 4 describes the dataset and the window that we work within while presenting our findings. Section 5 presents the empirical results and cross-sectoral comparisons that is the heart of our research. Section 6 summarizes all of our findings and entails future work that may be undertaken by fellow researchers.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Singularity Spectrum $f(\alpha)$, Mass Exponent $\tau(q)$, and Rényi Entropy

Let m be a measure distributed on a geometric support F , the underlying domain on which the process is defined. The geometric support of this study is the discrete time axis (trading days) on which the financial returns are studied. The local singularity strength (or Hölder exponent [17, 18]) $\alpha(t)$ at position t describes how the measure scales with respect to the box size s around that position:

$$m(s, t) \sim s^{\alpha(t)}. \quad (1)$$

This relation is best represented by a local scaling irregularity, where $\alpha(t)$ describes the intensity of the fluctuations near t ; smaller values correspond to more irregular, burst-like behavior, and larger values correspond to smoother regions. Classical self-similar processes are described by a single exponent, while multifractal systems display a series of scaling exponents over the support. In financial time series the underlying time variable is regularly spaced, but the measure obtained from log-returns gives rise to a heterogeneous, scale-dependent structure, due to volatility clustering and intermittent shocks. This calls for a multifractal description based on the spectrum [39].

Let $N_s(\alpha)$ be defined as the number of boxes of size s for which the local exponent is in

the range $[\alpha, \alpha + d\alpha]$. The scaling of this quantity defines the singularity spectrum [17]:

$$N_s(\alpha) \sim s^{-f(\alpha)}. \quad (2)$$

The function $f(\alpha)$ denotes the dimension wherein lie the subset of points showcasing identical singularity strength. This dimension was coined the term Hausdorff dimension in popular literature. In physical or visual terms, it quantifies how “dense” or “rare” certain fluctuation intensities are across the signal. For a monofractal process:

$$\alpha = H, \quad f(\alpha) = 1, \quad (3)$$

which is indicative of uniform scaling behaviour [28]. On the other hand, multifractals exhibit a continuous, concave distribution that assumes an inverted parabolic form. The width

$$\Delta\alpha = \alpha_{\max} - \alpha_{\min} \quad (4)$$

helps measure scaling heterogeneity in our time series [32]. In financial terms, this distance or width is an absolute measurement of the number of volatility regimes present in the time series under observation [40].

A better way to capture this statistically is by utilizing a partition function [17, 16]:

$$\chi(q, s) = \sum_t [m(s, t)]^q, \quad (5)$$

which scales as:

$$\chi(q, s) \sim s^{\tau(q)}. \quad (6)$$

Mass exponent function $\tau(q)$ depicts the changes in moment of the distribution depending on the scale. For mono-fractal structures, the relationship is linear; for multifractals, however, $\tau(q) = qH - 1$, is non-linear with respect to q .

The duality between these representations is given by the Legendre transform:

$$\alpha(q) = \frac{d\tau(q)}{dq}, \quad f(\alpha) = q\alpha - \tau(q). \quad (7)$$

This transform connects statistical scaling with singularity, and therefore gives a full description of the organization of the system at multiple scales. [41, 17].

Rényi entropy offers a better template to understand such scaling at a deeper level. For

a probability distribution $p_i(s)$, the Rényi entropy of order q [42] is defined as:

$$S_q(s) = \frac{1}{1-q} \log \sum_i [p_i(s)]^q. \quad (8)$$

Under scale invariance, $S_q(s) \sim D_q \log s$, where D_q are the generalised dimensions [43, 44], related to the mass exponent by:

$$\tau(q) = (q-1)D_q. \quad (9)$$

2.2 Generalised Hurst Exponents $H(q)$ and the Legendre Structure

In time-series analysis, multifractality is operationalised through the scaling of the q -th order fluctuation function:

$$F_q(s) \sim s^{H(q)}. \quad (10)$$

The generalised Hurst exponent $H(q)$ extends the classical Hurst exponent by allowing different moments to exhibit different scaling behaviour [28, 19]. As established in [28, 16], the relationship with the mass exponent is:

$$\tau(q) = qH(q) - 1. \quad (11)$$

A constant $H(q) = H$ implies monofractality, whereas a varying $H(q)$ indicates multifractality. Empirically, $H(q)$ is often a decreasing function of q , reflecting that large fluctuations are less persistent than small fluctuations and this strengthens the case with another concept cemented in financial theory known as mean-reversion [34, 45].

Applying the Legendre transform [41] yields:

$$\alpha(q) = H(q) + q \frac{dH(q)}{dq}, \quad f(\alpha) = q\alpha - \tau(q). \quad (12)$$

The condition $H(2) \approx 0.5$ is consistent with the absence of linear autocorrelation in returns, as required by the efficient market hypothesis [2]. However, this does not imply randomness in a stronger sense. Higher-order exponents reveal that financial markets possess memory in volatility and nonlinear dependencies [46, 47].

2.3 Sources of Multifractality and Financial Interpretation

The multifractality observed in financial time series arises from two distinct but interacting mechanisms: heavy-tailed distributions and non-linear temporal correlations. The

first source is the fat-tailed nature of returns, typically characterised by:

$$P(|r| > x) \sim x^{-\gamma}, \quad (13)$$

with empirical values $\gamma \approx 3$ [6, 5]. The second source is non-linear temporal correlation, which reflects genuine multiscale dynamics. To disentangle these effects, surrogate data techniques are employed [48, 49]. For a shuffled series, temporal correlations are destroyed while preserving the marginal distribution [50, 40]. The correlation-driven component is then given by:

$$\Delta\alpha_{\text{corr}} = \Delta\alpha - \Delta\alpha_{\text{shuf}}. \quad (14)$$

3 Methodology

3.1 Multifractal Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (MF-DFA)

The empirical analysis is conducted using the MF-DFA framework [28, 16]. Given a price process $P(t)$, the logarithmic return series is:

$$r(t) = \ln P(t) - \ln P(t-1). \quad (15)$$

The cumulative profile is:

$$Y(i) = \sum_{k=1}^i [r(k) - \langle r \rangle], \quad (16)$$

where $\langle r \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N r(t)$ is the sample mean.

The profile is partitioned into overlapping segments of length s , within which local polynomial trends are estimated and removed [29]. Denoting by $F_v(s)$ the root-mean-square fluctuation within segment v , the q -order fluctuation function is defined as:

$$F_q(s) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{v=1}^{N_s} [F_v(s)]^q \right)^{1/q}, & q \neq 0, \\ e^{\left(\frac{1}{2N_s} \sum_{v=1}^{N_s} \ln [F_v(s)]^2 \right)}, & q = 0. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The fluctuation function follows the power law which is in line with the scale invariance hypothesis, in Eq. (10).

3.2 Scaling Exponents and Multifractal Spectrum

The mass exponent function follows from Eq. (11) [28, 17]. The nonlinearity of $\tau(q)$ encapsulates a defining symptom of multifractality. Since the formulation incorporates both positive and negative moments q , negative values of $\tau(q)$ should not be interpreted as indicating lesser contributions. Rather, they reflect the scaling behaviour associated with small fluctuations, which are amplified for $q < 0$ [50, 16].

The singularity spectrum can be obtained through the Legendre transform in equation (7), whereas the spectral width $\Delta\alpha$ from Eq. (4) provides a measure of the multifractality of the time series.

3.3 Symmetric Fluctuation Analysis

Related asymmetric scaling approaches have been developed in [35, 36], though operating on trend direction rather than moment order, while distinct fractal properties between positive and negative returns have been documented in [51]. Here we introduce separate fluctuation functions $F_{+q}(s)$ and $F_{-q}(s)$ that are computed for positive and negative moment orders. Their relationship is quantified through the Pearson correlation coefficient computed across scales s :

$$\rho(q) = \frac{\sum_s (\log F_{+q}(s) - \langle \log F_{+q}(s) \rangle) (\log F_{-q}(s) - \langle \log F_{-q}(s) \rangle)}{\sqrt{\sum_s (\log F_{+q}(s) - \langle \log F_{+q}(s) \rangle)^2} \sqrt{\sum_s (\log F_{-q}(s) - \langle \log F_{-q}(s) \rangle)^2}}, \quad (18)$$

where averaging is done over all permissible scales. A $\rho(q) \approx 1$ would signify that large-scale fluctuations as well as small-scale fluctuations obey scaling with respect to each other on different scales, while departure from unity signifies asymmetry within the multifractal process.

3.4 Parameter Selection and Scaling Regime

The analysis is performed over a moderate scale s to balance the statistical reliability and multiscale effects [16]. A linear trend line model is fitted to the dataset to consider any possible noise in the residual part, and overlapping windows are used to get more effective data points [52, 53]. The value range for $q \in [-30, 30]$ is considered to observe various fluctuation phenomena [28, 54]. Higher positive values for q give prominence to large fluctuations in extreme situations in the market, while negative values focus on smaller fluctuations in quieter market periods.

4 Data

The analysis involves the use of data from 50 financial assets. The list includes stocks in various sectors, commodities, cryptos and foreign exchange traded funds. The period covered by the study is from January 2010 to April 2026. Prices per day for each asset are extracted and all non-positive observations are removed. The data is then divided into six categories:

1. **Large Cap Technology:** AAPL, MSFT, GOOG, AMZN, NVDA, META, TSLA, NFLX, AMD, INTC
2. **Financials:** JPM, BAC, GS, MS, WFC, BLK, C, AXP, V, MA
3. **Healthcare & Consumer:** JNJ, PFE, UNH, MRK, ABBV, PG, KO, PEP, WMT, COST
4. **Energy & Industrials:** XOM, CVX, COP, BA, CAT, GE, HON, LMT, RTX, UPS
5. **Commodities & Crypto:** GC=F (Gold), SI=F (Silver), CL=F (Crude Oil), BTC-USD, ETH-USD
6. **International ETFs:** EWJ, EWZ, FXI, EWG, EWU

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Scaling Behaviour and Fluctuation Functions

Power-law scaling is demonstrated through the empirical analysis in all analyzed securities; hence, the application of the MF-DFA technique is validated for return processes [28, 55]. The dependence $F_q(s) \sim s^{H(q)}$ works for a wide intermediate scale interval. The linear-like character of these graphs on log-log scale means that the process of detrending was successfully implemented without losing the information about the internal dynamics.

One of the main peculiarities in the obtained results is the systematic divergence of the fluctuation functions corresponding to various values of moment orders q , as illustrated for AAPL in Figure 1. As follows from the analysis, the curves describing the cases of large positive values of q correspond to extreme cases, which are characterized by a stronger degree of scaling. Negative values of q are associated with small fluctuations [16, 56]. The widening distance between these curves proves heterogeneous scaling.

Figure 1: Multifractal properties of AAPL daily log returns (2010–2026) from the MF-DFA method: (a) time series plot of daily log returns; (b) log-log plots of fluctuation functions $F_q(s)$ in the range of $q \in [-30, +30]$; (c) generalized Hurst exponent $H(q)$; (d) scaling exponent $\tau(q)$; (e) singularity strength $\alpha(q)$; and (f) multifractal spectrum $f(\alpha)$

5.2 Multifractal Spectra: Width $\Delta\alpha$ and Sectoral Variation

The multifractal spectra $f(\alpha)$ that have been computed through the use of the Legendre transform have shown a consistently concave shape among all tested assets, confirming the existence of robust multifractality in the evolution of financial returns.

Results from empirical analysis have highlighted a significant degree of cross-sectional dispersion in $\Delta\alpha$, which indicates the importance of heterogeneity in terms of the impact of market microstructure. Large capitalization and technology stocks such as AAPL and MSFT have demonstrated only moderate degrees of multifractality, which suggests the existence of an equilibrium between efficiency and persistent correlations in their evolution. Conversely, volatile stocks that belong to the category of growth stocks such as TSLA and INTC have demonstrated higher degrees of multifractality, which implies the greater degree of regime dependence and volatility clustering.

One especially interesting phenomenon to observe has been the occurrence of higher multifractality in defensive and consumer goods stocks such as KO, PEP, and JNJ, which are known for being low-volatility assets.

The complete set of estimated values is reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Multifractal spectral width ($\Delta\alpha$) estimated via MF-DFA for all assets (2010–2026).

Ticker	Asset Name	$\Delta\alpha$
<i>Large Cap Technology</i>		
AAPL	Apple Inc.	0.4913
MSFT	Microsoft Corp.	0.4881
GOOG	Alphabet Inc.	0.3538
AMZN	Amazon.com Inc.	0.4870
NVDA	NVIDIA Corp.	0.1812
META	Meta Platforms Inc.	0.4263
TSLA	Tesla Inc.	0.5141
NFLX	Netflix Inc.	0.2741
AMD	Advanced Micro Devices	0.3653
INTC	Intel Corp.	0.5367
<i>Financials</i>		
JPM	JPMorgan Chase & Co.	0.4403
BAC	Bank of America Corp.	0.4103
GS	Goldman Sachs Group	0.5816
MS	Morgan Stanley	0.5421
WFC	Wells Fargo & Co.	0.3429
BLK	BlackRock Inc.	0.5819
C	Citigroup Inc.	0.5251
AXP	American Express Co.	0.6109
V	Visa Inc.	0.5382
MA	Mastercard Inc.	0.6367
<i>Healthcare & Consumer</i>		
JNJ	Johnson & Johnson	0.7528
PFE	Pfizer Inc.	0.5810
UNH	UnitedHealth Group	0.4478
MRK	Merck & Co.	0.4189
ABBV	AbbVie Inc.	0.5511
PG	Procter & Gamble Co.	0.5583
KO	Coca-Cola Co.	0.8235
PEP	PepsiCo Inc.	0.7841
WMT	Walmart Inc.	0.5343
COST	Costco Wholesale Corp.	0.5089

Ticker	Asset Name	$\Delta\alpha$
<i>Energy & Industrials</i>		
XOM	Exxon Mobil Corp.	0.6154
CVX	Chevron Corp.	0.6624
COP	ConocoPhillips	0.5968
BA	Boeing Co.	0.6929
CAT	Caterpillar Inc.	0.6093
GE	GE Aerospace	0.5722
HON	Honeywell Intl.	0.6383
LMT	Lockheed Martin Corp.	0.6708
RTX	RTX Corp.	0.6520
UPS	United Parcel Service	0.4452
<i>Commodities & Crypto</i>		
GC=F	Gold Futures	0.5350
SI=F	Silver Futures	0.5113
CL=F	Crude Oil Futures	0.6656
BTC-USD	Bitcoin	0.5801
ETH-USD	Ethereum	0.5999
<i>International ETFs</i>		
EWJ	iShares MSCI Japan ETF	0.6141
EWZ	iShares MSCI Brazil ETF	0.6235
FXI	iShares China Large-Cap ETF	0.4846
EWG	iShares MSCI Germany ETF	0.6704
EWU	iShares MSCI UK ETF	0.6815

5.3 Symmetric Fluctuation Analysis

Based on the analysis of the symmetric MF-DFA using the comparison of $F_{+q}(s)$ and $F_{-q}(s)$, the results indicate that there are highly non-trivial correlations among all sectors analyzed. The actual numerical value for the Pearson correlation coefficients are provided in Table 2, whereas the time evolution of each sector is provided in Figure 2

In all stocks, Pearson correlations tend towards unity for small values of $|q|$, representing standard trading practices and arbitrageurs' actions to ensure the approximate balance in movements of prices in both directions [10]. However, as $|q|$ becomes larger, Table 2 and Figure 2 unambiguously show a drop in correlation for nearly all asset categories, which implies that extreme price changes depend on intrinsic characteristics of the stock in the multifractal partition function [28]. The decrease in correlation is particularly noticeable

for defensive and staple companies like PEP and KO, where correlation decreases sharply for high values of $|q|$: the lowest correlation $\rho = -0.1332$ is found for PEP [51, 35].

For financial industry stocks like MA, BLK, AXP, and GS, there are notable fluctuations for high values of q as expected from asymmetric shock amplification due to leverage effects and systemic risk transmission through negative feedback mechanisms [11, 57] with a gradual emergence of positive trends [58]. This behavior is in line with the notion of non-linear shock propagation at different scales under the framework of renormalization [38, 59]. On the other hand, technology sector stocks like AAPL, MSFT, GOOG, and AMZN have rather stable correlations up to higher values of $|q|$, implying a more symmetric impact of extreme shocks possibly because of deeper liquidity and efficient information [55, 60].

Figure 2: Pearson correlation between $F_{+q}(s)$ and $F_{-q}(s)$ across moment orders $|q| = 1-30$ (MF-DFA, log-returns, 2010–2026). The closer the value is to one, the more symmetrical it is; otherwise, a significant drop for higher $|q|$ (KO, PEP, JNJ, CVX, and CL=F)

Table 2: Pearson correlation range (Min ρ , Max ρ) via MF-DFA for all assets (2010–2026).

Ticker	Asset Name	Min ρ	Max ρ
<i>Large Cap Technology</i>			
AAPL	Apple Inc.	0.9700	0.9998
MSFT	Microsoft Corp.	0.9233	0.9999
GOOG	Alphabet Inc.	0.9692	0.9994
AMZN	Amazon.com Inc.	0.9744	0.9999
NVDA	NVIDIA Corp.	0.9706	0.9996
META	Meta Platforms Inc.	0.9287	0.9979
TSLA	Tesla Inc.	0.9324	0.9995
NFLX	Netflix Inc.	0.9841	0.9990
AMD	Advanced Micro Devices	0.9871	0.9999
INTC	Intel Corp.	0.9314	0.9997
<i>Financials</i>			
JPM	JPMorgan Chase & Co.	0.9842	0.9995
BAC	Bank of America Corp.	0.9786	0.9998
GS	Goldman Sachs Group	0.9468	0.9998
MS	Morgan Stanley	0.9570	0.9996
WFC	Wells Fargo & Co.	0.9600	0.9989
BLK	BlackRock Inc.	0.8859	1.0000
C	Citigroup Inc.	0.9583	0.9990
AXP	American Express Co.	0.9754	0.9997
V	Visa Inc.	0.8369	0.9998
MA	Mastercard Inc.	0.7516	0.9993
<i>Healthcare & Consumer</i>			
JNJ	Johnson & Johnson	0.3982	0.9997
PFE	Pfizer Inc.	0.9219	0.9997
UNH	UnitedHealth Group	0.9313	0.9996
MRK	Merck & Co.	0.8861	0.9995
ABBV	AbbVie Inc.	0.9465	0.9998
PG	Procter & Gamble Co.	0.8195	0.9999
KO	Coca-Cola Co.	0.2383	0.9997
PEP	PepsiCo Inc.	-0.1332	0.9994
WMT	Walmart Inc.	0.9644	0.9999
COST	Costco Wholesale Corp.	0.9240	0.9995
<i>Energy & Industrials</i>			

Ticker	Asset Name	Min ρ	Max ρ
XOM	Exxon Mobil Corp.	0.9296	0.9994
CVX	Chevron Corp.	0.5253	0.9995
COP	ConocoPhillips	0.8458	0.9996
BA	Boeing Co.	0.9045	0.9995
CAT	Caterpillar Inc.	0.9604	0.9996
GE	GE Aerospace	0.9450	0.9996
HON	Honeywell Intl.	0.9355	0.9998
LMT	Lockheed Martin Corp.	0.7087	0.9999
RTX	RTX Corp.	0.9667	0.9998
UPS	United Parcel Service	0.9684	0.9997
<i>Commodities & Crypto</i>			
GC=F	Gold Futures	0.9118	0.9998
SI=F	Silver Futures	0.8545	0.9998
CL=F	Crude Oil Futures	0.7178	0.9997
BTC-USD	Bitcoin	0.9769	0.9990
ETH-USD	Ethereum	0.9670	0.9996
<i>International ETFs</i>			
EWJ	iShares MSCI Japan ETF	0.9581	0.9999
EWZ	iShares MSCI Brazil ETF	0.9320	0.9999
FXI	iShares China Large-Cap ETF	0.9464	0.9997
EWG	iShares MSCI Germany ETF	0.8940	0.9996
EWU	iShares MSCI UK ETF	0.8699	0.9997

5.4 Market Inefficiency Interpretation

The scaling behavior seen in the fluctuation function constitutes empirical evidence that contradicts the weak-form efficiency market hypothesis [2, 3]. In an efficient market, the scaling exponent should be a constant value, $H(q) \approx 0.5$, meaning that the fluctuations are memoryless, i.e., there is no correlation between them [4, 1]. The explicit dependency of the scaling exponent on q suggests that the return series has long-range correlations and non-linear dependences [28, 16].

Moreover, the difference between fluctuation curves calculated for different values of q points at the possibility that large and small fluctuations follow different dynamic mechanisms [32, 33]. This violates the idea of homogeneous scaling implied by classical models such as geometric Brownian motion [4, 12]. The results suggest that information is integrated into prices in a heterogeneous and scale-dependent fashion [47, 61], resulting in

sustained volatility and the clustering of extreme events [10, 45].

5.5 Cumulant-Based Characteristic Function Scaling

For a log-return displacement $\Delta r(\tau, t) = r(\tau + t) - r(\tau)$ over horizon t from origin τ , define the scaled log-characteristic function and its k^2 -normalised counterpart:

$$s_k(t) = \frac{1}{t} \ln \left| \langle e^{ik\Delta r(t)} \rangle \right|, \quad D_k(t) = \frac{s_k(t)}{k^2}, \quad (19)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the ensemble average over N_{orig} starting origins, with N_{orig} determined by the window size as described below. The motivation for the k^2 normalisation follows from the cumulant expansion of the log-characteristic function [10, 6]:

$$D_k(t) = -\frac{\kappa_2(t)}{2t} - \frac{\kappa_4(t)}{4!t} k^2 - \frac{\kappa_6(t)}{6!t} k^4 - \dots \quad (20)$$

Under Gaussianity all cumulants $\kappa_n = 0$ for $n \geq 3$, so $D_k = -\sigma^2/2$ is constant in both k and t [1, 4]. Departure from k -constancy is therefore a direct, model-free measure of higher-order cumulant contributions—equivalently, of leptokurtosis and fat tails—at horizon t [5, 6]. Temporal non-constancy of $s_k(t)$ at fixed k additionally implies dependence or non-stationarity in the increment distribution, since for any process with stationary independent increments the characteristic exponent factorises as $\ln |\phi(k, t)| = t\psi(k)$, forcing $s_k(t)$ to be constant in t [10, 28].

5.5.1 Multi-Window Backtracking Procedure

The diagnostic is applied across eight rolling windows of size

$$W \in \{500, 1000, 2000, 3000, 5000, 7500, 10000, 15000\} \quad (\text{trading days}). \quad (21)$$

Rather than anchoring windows at their start dates, each window is constructed by *backtracking* from a fixed terminal date of 11th April 2026: the most recent W trading days up to and including 11th April 2026 are selected, so that all windows share a common right endpoint and differ only in how far back into history they reach. This approach makes sure that the results always depend upon the latest market state and takes progressively longer historical periods into account as the window size (W) grows. For example, the period for a 500-day window corresponds roughly to 2024-2026, the 5000-day window goes back to roughly 2006-2026, thereby covering the financial crisis of 2008-2009, while the 15000-day window goes back to the early 1960s for securities with that long a history.

For every window, possible values of the horizon are limited by $t \leq W/2$ and the number

of origins by $N_{\text{orig}} = W - 1 - \max(t)$. The wave-number set is $\mathcal{K} = \{0.5, 1, 2, \dots, 10\}$.

A horizon t is flagged as exhibiting practically significant non-constancy if the relative range across reliable wave numbers,

$$\delta_{\text{rel}}(t) = \frac{\max_k D_k(t) - \min_k D_k(t)}{\langle |D_k(t)| \rangle_k}, \quad (22)$$

exceeds $\delta^* = 5\%$, with at least four reliable estimates ($|\hat{\phi}(k, t)| \geq 0.30$) and coverage $\geq 60\%$ of $|\mathcal{K}|$.

To aggregate flagged short-horizon non-constancy into a single interpretable scalar, we define the **Spectral Cumulant Index** (SCI), denoted Γ , for a given ticker and window as:

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}^*|} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}^*} \min(\delta_{\text{rel}}(t), 5), \quad (23)$$

where $\mathcal{T}^* = \{t \leq 20 : t \text{ is flagged}\}$ is the set of flagged short-term horizons and the cap of 5 prevents a single extreme horizon from dominating the index. If no short horizons are flagged, $\Gamma = 0$. The ticker-level SCI, $\bar{\Gamma}$, is obtained by averaging Γ across all valid windows. Larger values of $\bar{\Gamma}$ indicate that the asset's return distribution exhibits stronger and more persistent departures from Gaussian second-cumulant dominance across investment horizons. The Spearman rank correlation $\rho_s(k, D_k)$ is reported alongside for directional characterisation.

5.5.2 Cross-Sectional Results

Of the 50 assets examined, 43 exhibit $\bar{\Gamma} > 0$ in at least one window, indicating that practically significant non-constancy of D_k is pervasive across asset classes. Seven assets—CAT, EWJ, GC=F, JNJ, GOOG, PFE, and SI=F—record $\bar{\Gamma} = 0$ across all windows examined, suggesting that their return distributions remain within the Gaussian tolerance at the scales and horizons tested, with the second cumulant dominating throughout [16, 28]

The financials sector dominates the cross-sectional ranking by $\bar{\Gamma}$. Citigroup (C, $\bar{\Gamma} = 0.157$), Morgan Stanley (MS, 0.129), and Bank of America (BAC, 0.125) record the three highest values in the full universe, followed by UnitedHealth Group (UNH, 0.110) from Healthcare & Consumer and Netflix (NFLX, 0.106) from Technology. This ranking of all tickers by their respective values of k -constancy violations for each window size is presented in Table 3. For all ticker-window combinations where a violation was detected, these violations continue to cluster around time scales $t \leq 20$, in line with the expected behavior of the cumulant-based formula for $D_k(t)$ given by Eq. (20), under which the contribution of higher-order cumulants diminishes in comparison to variance as the scale

increases, eventually resulting in $D_k(t)$ becoming independent of k regardless of the tail thickness [5, 7]. The Spearman rank correlation between k and $D_k(t)$ is positive for all detected violations, suggesting that the non-constancy is always in the form of an increase of leptokurtic tails [6, 10].

Table 3: Spectral Cumulant Index $\bar{\Gamma}$ by ticker, average value among all possible windows using backwards tracking (terminal date 11 April 2026), arranged in descending order. Column Peak Window indicates W , at which Γ attains its maximum value for the given ticker. Securities with $\bar{\Gamma} = 0$ satisfy k -Constancy at all horizons in every window.

Ticker	Sector	$\bar{\Gamma}$	Peak W (days)
C	Financials	0.1569	5000
MS	Financials	0.1285	5000
BAC	Financials	0.1245	5000
UNH	Healthcare & Consumer	0.1096	10000
NFLX	Tech	0.1057	1000
ETH-USD	Commodities & Crypto	0.1013	3000
META	Tech	0.0967	1000
WFC	Financials	0.0961	5000
AMD	Tech	0.0948	3000
AXP	Financials	0.0800	3000
AAPL	Tech	0.0748	7500
JPM	Financials	0.0732	5000
GS	Financials	0.0664	5000
EWZ	Intl ETFs	0.0662	2000
INTC	Tech	0.0632	500
NVDA	Tech	0.0632	3000
TSLA	Tech	0.0587	2000
BA	Energy & Industrials	0.0541	3000
COP	Energy & Industrials	0.0508	2000
PG	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0500	10000
HON	Energy & Industrials	0.0480	10000
BLK	Financials	0.0443	5000
CVX	Energy & Industrials	0.0434	2000
MA	Financials	0.0367	5000
MSFT	Tech	0.0345	10000
BTC-USD	Commodities & Crypto	0.0335	3000
V	Financials	0.0335	2000
XOM	Energy & Industrials	0.0308	10000

Ticker	Sector	$\bar{\Gamma}$	Peak W (days)
ABBV	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0307	2000
RTX	Energy & Industrials	0.0296	3000
FXI	Intl ETFs	0.0295	5000
EWU	Intl ETFs	0.0292	5000
GE	Energy & Industrials	0.0262	3000
LMT	Energy & Industrials	0.0248	15000
PEP	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0245	2000
WMT	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0164	2000
KO	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0162	10000
AMZN	Tech	0.0159	5000
UPS	Energy & Industrials	0.0141	500
CL=F	Commodities & Crypto	0.0100	5000
COST	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0094	1000
EWG	Intl ETFs	0.0087	2000
MRK	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0074	7500
CAT	Energy & Industrials	0.0000	—
EWJ	Intl ETFs	0.0000	—
GC=F	Commodities & Crypto	0.0000	—
JNJ	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0000	—
GOOG	Tech	0.0000	—
PFE	Healthcare & Consumer	0.0000	—
SI=F	Commodities & Crypto	0.0000	—

5.5.3 Window-Dependence and Regime Sensitivity

One important observation missing from single-window calculations is the trend of varying Γ for different window sizes using the same ticker. For BAC, C, MS, and WFC—representative of major financials, Γ becomes very large for windows of 5000 days and more. Given that all windows go back from 11th April 2026, a 5000-day window corresponds roughly to 2006; hence, it takes in the entire period of the financial crisis of 2008–2009. The non-Gaussian tail structure that arises from balance-sheet distress, fire sales, and systemic risk propagation during this crisis is thus seen in high Γ values at large windows [11, 57]. On the other hand, META and NFLX have high Γ at intermediate windows of 1000–3000 days, corresponding roughly to 2020–2022 from 11th April 2026, capturing changes in their return distribution due to structural breaks in revenue regime that arise from platform effects. They become less prominent once windows go further back into the pre-maturity trading history of the two tickers. This dependence on window

size, thus, shows that Γ is regime-dependent rather than a constant property of the asset, and single-window estimates will tend to underestimate or overestimate Γ depending on the historical episode being captured within the backtracking horizon [45, 47].

Figure 3: Four-panel s_k/D_k diagnostic for AAPL at the 7500-day backtracked window (terminal date 11th April 2026, spanning approximately 1996–2026, $N_{\text{orig}} = 5499$ origins). *Top-left*: $D_k(t)$ vs. horizon t for each $k \in \mathcal{K}$, coloured by k . *Top-right*: D_k vs. k at all candidate horizons; dashed lines show the reliable- k mean and \times markers denote excluded points ($|\hat{\phi}| < 0.30$). *Bottom panels*: Unfiltered $s_k(t)$ versus t and k . Red dashed vertical lines denote selected horizons. The consistent kurtosis of D_k as a function of k , with $\rho_s \geq +0.97$ for all selected horizons, implies that the distribution remains consistently leptokurtic at short to medium horizons, with $\Gamma = 0.174$ at this window.

5.5.4 AAPL: Case Study

For technology stocks, $\bar{\Gamma} = 0.0748$ peaks in the 7500-day window, starting around mid-1996 and ending in 2026 (from 11th April 2026). In the peak window, AAPL receives a flag at six short-term horizons where δ_{rel} varies between 10.8% and 24.9% with $\rho_s \in [+0.97, +1.00]$ across the board. The four-panel test for the window is displayed in

Figure 3.

Here we observe two salient properties. The first is that flags occur mainly at $t \leq 20$ days in all the windows where AAPL experiences $\Gamma > 0$. This aligns with the cumulative average effect discussed previously with respect to Eq. (20). The second is that AAPL exhibits positive values of Γ in six out of seven windows for which enough historical data exists, indicating that fat tails are a persistent characteristic of its return distribution and not a consequence of a particular event during backtracking starting from 11th April 2026 [8, 9]. The uniformly positive Spearman correlations show that $|D_k|$ monotonically increases with k , a hallmark of fat tails in the frequency domain [5, 10]. They lend support to AAPL's high Pearson correlation floor ($\min \rho = 0.9700$) between F_{+q} and F_{-q} [51], and are consistent with its multifractal spectral width $\Delta\alpha = 0.4913$ [55, 16].

5.6 Characteristic Function Geometry and Box-Counting Fractal Dimension

As a supplement to MF-DFA, we study the geometrical complexity of the empirical characteristic function trajectory in the complex plane. For a time-series return $\{r(t)\}_{t=1}^N$, the empirical characteristic function with respect to moment order q can be expressed by the cumulation sum:

$$\Phi(t; q) = \sum_{k=1}^t e^{iqr(k)}, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (24)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}$ is a frequency factor determining what portion of the return distribution is amplified. The expression $e^{iqr(k)}$ is a complex number of unit modulus whose phase $qr(k)$ depends linearly on the return $r(k)$ as a function of q . When $|q|$ is small, each increment makes a very gradual rotation, while the path $\Phi(t; q)$ is smooth and almost straight. In contrast, for large $|q|$, the increments make quicker and finer rotations in response to the return, thus the path winds around in a highly folded manner and gains in geometric complexity [62]. This mapping of equation (24) converts the complete distributional information in the returns sequence into geometric information of a curve in \mathbb{R}^2 defined by:

$$\Phi(t; q) = \sum_{k=1}^t \cos(qr(k)) + i \sum_{k=1}^t \sin(qr(k)). \quad (25)$$

The complexity of the obtained curve measured geometrically can be characterized by means of the box-counting fractal dimension D_{box} [63, 64]. The process starts with

normalization to unit square as follows:

$$\tilde{x}(t) = \frac{\operatorname{Re} \Phi(t; q) - \min_t \operatorname{Re} \Phi}{\max(\operatorname{span}_x, \operatorname{span}_y)}, \quad \tilde{y}(t) = \frac{\operatorname{Im} \Phi(t; q) - \min_t \operatorname{Im} \Phi}{\max(\operatorname{span}_x, \operatorname{span}_y)}, \quad (26)$$

where $\operatorname{span}_x = \max_t \operatorname{Re} \Phi - \min_t \operatorname{Re} \Phi$ and $\operatorname{span}_y = \max_t \operatorname{Im} \Phi - \min_t \operatorname{Im} \Phi$ are the coordinate ranges, and the denominator uses their maximum to preserve the aspect ratio of the curve. The normalised plane is then partitioned into a regular grid of square boxes of side length ε , and the number of occupied boxes—those containing at least one point of the curve—is counted:

$$N(\varepsilon) = \# \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid \exists t : \left\lfloor \frac{\tilde{x}(t)}{\varepsilon} \right\rfloor = i \text{ and } \left\lfloor \frac{\tilde{y}(t)}{\varepsilon} \right\rfloor = j \right\}, \quad (27)$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor function. For a self-similar curve of fractal dimension D_{box} , the occupied count scales as a power law in the box size [64, 63]

$$N(\varepsilon) \sim \varepsilon^{-D_{\text{box}}}, \quad (28)$$

so that D_{box} is recovered as the negative slope of the log-log regression:

$$\log N(\varepsilon) = -D_{\text{box}} \log \varepsilon + C, \quad (29)$$

estimated by ordinary least squares over $n = 20$ logarithmically spaced scales $\varepsilon \in [\varepsilon_{\min}, \varepsilon_{\max}]$, with $\varepsilon_{\min} = 2/N$ and $\varepsilon_{\max} = 0.20$. The lower bound makes sure that each box can hold at least two points on the curve that are next to each other. The upper bound keeps the global shape from being more important than the fine local structure. A Euclidean smooth curve has a box dimension of 1, and a plane-filling curve has a box dimension of 2 [63]. All fractal curves fall between these two values.

The goodness of fit is assessed by the coefficient of determination:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{\varepsilon} (\log N(\varepsilon) - \widehat{\log N}(\varepsilon))^2}{\sum_{\varepsilon} (\log N(\varepsilon) - \overline{\log N})^2}, \quad (30)$$

where $\widehat{\log N}(\varepsilon)$ is the fitted value from Eq. (29) and $\overline{\log N}$ is the mean over all scales. Values of R^2 exceeds 0.97 across all assets and moment orders. This confirm that the power-law hypothesis in Eq. (28) holds and that D_{box} is a well-identified quantity [16].

The analysis is conducted for $q \in \{1, 10, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200\}$ on four representative assets: AAPL, BTC-USD, PEP, and GC=F. The paths are observed at five different zoom levels, with the strongest point of the curve being the 1–99 percentile midpoint.

These levels are $(1\times)$, $2\times$, $4\times$, $8\times$, and $16\times$. Table 4 reports the estimated dimensions. At $q = 1$, all assets yield $D_{\text{box}} \approx 1.00$, consistent with a near-rectifiable curve, as the slow rotation of unit-modulus increments at small frequency produces a path with negligible self-intersection and folding [64]. As q increases, D_{box} rises for most assets, reaching values between 0.98 and 1.21 at $q = 200$, reflecting the amplification of high-frequency oscillatory structure as the path integrates progressively more extreme return contributions [6, 10] Several high-volatility assets—including AMD, TSLA, NFLX, ETH-USD, and CL=F—exhibit a non-monotone pattern in which D_{box} peaks at an intermediate moment order and then declines, indicating that at sufficiently large frequencies the path saturates its space-filling capacity within the estimation window [16, 28]

Table 4: Box-counting fractal dimension D_{box} of the characteristic function path $\Phi(t; q)$ for all assets across moment orders q (log-returns, 2010–2026). All $R^2 > 0.97$.

Ticker	$q = 1$	$q = 10$	$q = 50$	$q = 75$	$q = 100$	$q = 150$	$q = 200$
<i>Large Cap Technology</i>							
AAPL	0.9962	1.0110	1.0579	1.0820	1.1044	1.1363	1.1829
MSFT	0.9964	1.0066	1.0486	1.0735	1.0940	1.1309	1.1720
GOOG	0.9962	1.0081	1.0572	1.0776	1.0924	1.1392	1.1487
AMZN	0.9966	1.0119	1.0648	1.0947	1.1170	1.1605	1.1158
NVDA	0.9963	1.0157	1.0906	1.1211	1.1672	1.1735	1.0771
META	0.9941	1.0130	1.0653	1.0937	1.1279	1.1571	1.0794
TSLA	0.9972	1.0222	1.1068	1.1549	1.1729	1.1454	1.0190
NFLX	0.9979	1.0207	1.0871	1.1327	1.1680	1.1514	1.0089
AMD	0.9967	1.0215	1.1145	1.1681	1.1984	0.9720	0.9787
INTC	0.9958	1.0110	1.0648	1.0947	1.1156	1.1649	1.1721
<i>Financials</i>							
JPM	0.9964	1.0077	1.0529	1.0772	1.0967	1.1382	1.1713
BAC	0.9961	1.0111	1.0654	1.0945	1.1218	1.1847	1.1845
GS	0.9959	1.0095	1.0609	1.0889	1.1199	1.1573	1.1438
MS	0.9960	1.0131	1.0667	1.0873	1.1161	1.1610	1.1704
WFC	0.9958	1.0090	1.0596	1.0840	1.1078	1.1639	1.1863
BLK	0.9960	1.0094	1.0544	1.0806	1.0982	1.1527	1.1690
C	0.9958	1.0118	1.0655	1.0921	1.1210	1.1680	1.1925
AXP	0.9959	1.0082	1.0494	1.0727	1.0971	1.1297	1.1473
V	0.9962	1.0072	1.0479	1.0658	1.0819	1.1138	1.1235
MA	0.9960	1.0091	1.0463	1.0688	1.0843	1.1118	1.1292
<i>Healthcare & Consumer</i>							
JNJ	0.9958	1.0043	1.0342	1.0507	1.0658	1.0954	1.1306

Ticker	$q = 1$	$q = 10$	$q = 50$	$q = 75$	$q = 100$	$q = 150$	$q = 200$
PFE	0.9958	1.0063	1.0471	1.0671	1.0912	1.1337	1.1823
UNH	0.9961	1.0076	1.0501	1.0739	1.0967	1.1274	1.1546
MRK	0.9958	1.0039	1.0434	1.0679	1.0827	1.1279	1.1632
ABBV	0.9935	1.0063	1.0502	1.0711	1.0954	1.1236	1.1484
PG	0.9958	1.0027	1.0340	1.0510	1.0649	1.0976	1.1261
KO	0.9958	1.0039	1.0373	1.0486	1.0620	1.0944	1.1337
PEP	0.9958	1.0032	1.0320	1.0551	1.0643	1.0999	1.1382
WMT	0.9959	1.0051	1.0354	1.0538	1.0688	1.1011	1.1336
COST	0.9961	1.0049	1.0419	1.0581	1.0798	1.1124	1.1422
<i>Energy & Industrials</i>							
XOM	0.9958	1.0077	1.0510	1.0746	1.1008	1.1419	1.1744
CVX	0.9958	1.0063	1.0523	1.0729	1.0968	1.1320	1.1426
COP	0.9958	1.0110	1.0670	1.0981	1.1311	1.1669	1.1447
BA	0.9963	1.0113	1.0630	1.0892	1.1081	1.1462	1.1489
CAT	0.9959	1.0102	1.0625	1.0899	1.1141	1.1634	1.1664
GE	0.9959	1.0096	1.0621	1.0900	1.1143	1.1600	1.1670
HON	0.9962	1.0060	1.0445	1.0630	1.0855	1.1244	1.1452
LMT	0.9963	1.0058	1.0415	1.0608	1.0737	1.1036	1.1280
RTX	0.9958	1.0060	1.0465	1.0656	1.0896	1.1207	1.1596
UPS	0.9958	1.0077	1.0436	1.0641	1.0846	1.1170	1.1457
<i>Commodities & Crypto</i>							
GC=F	0.9958	1.0018	1.0388	1.0519	1.0679	1.0939	1.1204
SI=F	0.9959	1.0097	1.0606	1.0902	1.1161	1.1639	1.2079
CL=F	0.9967	1.0132	1.0741	1.1022	1.1260	1.1230	1.0673
BTC-USD	0.9988	1.0231	1.0794	1.1094	1.1463	1.1546	1.1394
ETH-USD	0.9952	1.0287	1.1305	1.1715	1.1628	1.1172	1.0572
<i>International ETFs</i>							
EWJ	0.9958	1.0007	1.0379	1.0531	1.0722	1.1043	1.1269
EWZ	0.9958	1.0111	1.0716	1.1055	1.1396	1.1624	1.0966
FXI	0.9958	1.0061	1.0593	1.0919	1.1197	1.1653	1.2010
EWG	0.9958	1.0056	1.0440	1.0621	1.0818	1.1058	1.1371
EWU	0.9958	1.0035	1.0375	1.0565	1.0675	1.0912	1.1129

BTC-USD exhibits one of the steepest initial rises in D_{box} , consistent with its elevated volatility and broader multifractal spectrum $\Delta\alpha = 0.5801$ [65, 66] Notably, D_{box} for BTC-USD peaks at $q = 150$ ($D_{\text{box}} = 1.1546$) and marginally declines to 1.1394 at $q = 200$,

suggesting that at sufficiently large frequencies the path begins to saturate its space-filling capacity within the estimation window, attributable to finite sample size and the bounded support of the normalised domain [28]. ETH-USD shows an even stronger effect of the kind, with a maximum of $D_{\text{box}} = 1.1715$ at $q = 75$ decreasing to 1.0572 for $q = 200$. This is caused by the increased influence of extreme moment orders on the return distribution of Ethereum. The asset showing a steady rise in D_{box} with q and being monotonically increasing for all $q \in [10; 200]$ is GC=F ($D_{\text{box}} = 1.0018$ at $q = 10$ increasing to $D_{\text{box}} = 1.1204$ for $q = 200$). PEP, being low-volatility, demonstrates a behavior similar to that of AAPL for all moment orders, which strengthens the case for its wide singularity spectrum and sharp Pearson correlation decline observed in Section 5.3 [67, 32]

Figure 4 shows how the complexity evolves geometrically for AAPL as the moment order increases at a magnification of $16\times$. The incremental rise in the value of D_{box} from 1.0579 at $q = 50$ to 1.1829 at $q = 200$ is directly interpretable as increased convolution density [55]. This high convolution density is a global feature of the graph as opposed to a local one [64, 63] as confirmed by the full-path view in Figure 5.

Gaspard et al. [68] established that in a chaotic diffusive system, the Hausdorff dimension of the hydrodynamic mode of wavenumber k obeys

$$D_H(k) = 1 + \frac{D}{\lambda} k^2 + \mathcal{O}(k^4), \quad (31)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient and λ is the maximal Lyapunov exponent. The fractal excess $\delta \equiv D_H - 1$ grows with the ratio D/λ , meaning that systems with stronger diffusion relative to their chaotic sensitivity exhibit greater geometric complexity in their invariant structures [13]. The empirical excess $D_{\text{box}}(q) - 1$ computed here plays an analogous role to δ , and the moment order q enters similarly to the wavenumber k , as both control the resolution at which fine structure in the underlying distribution is amplified. The near-parabolic growth of $D_{\text{box}}(q) - 1$ with q visible in Table 4 is qualitatively consistent with the quadratic scaling predicted by Eq. (31) at small moment orders, before finite-sample effects suppress further growth at large q in high-volatility assets such as ETH-USD and AMD [15].

The implied dynamical ratio is calculated as follows:

$$\lambda_{\text{implied}}(q, t) = \frac{D_k(t) \cdot q^2}{D_{\text{box}}(q) - 1} \quad (32)$$

This ratio is estimated for each asset across all moment orders $q \in \{10, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200\}$ and all available horizons t . The results across moment orders are summarised in Table 5, and the horizon-resolved decay is reported in Table 6. Seven assets—GOOG, JNJ, PFE, CAT, GC=F, SI=F, and EWJ—record $\lambda_{\text{implied}} = 0$ across all q and t , consistent with

Figure 4: Characteristic function paths $\Phi(t; q)$ for AAPL log-returns (2010–2026) at 16 \times zoom for $q \in \{50, 75, 100, 200\}$. The progressively increasing level of density of path convolutions with moment order is clearly visible; for example, D_{box} increases from 1.0579 when $q = 50$ to 1.1829 for $q = 200$. This shows that an increase in the moment order leads to greater geometric intricacy of the characteristic function path [64, 63]

Figure 5: Path of characteristic function $\Phi(t; q = 200)$ for AAPL log-return data (2010–2026). Estimated box dimension of $D_{\text{box}} = 1.1829$ ($R^2 > 0.999$) is the largest value among all moment orders for AAPL, which clearly indicates that the gradual rise in geometric complexity shown in Figure 4 persists globally and is not confined to the zoomed central region.

Gaussian second-cumulant dominance throughout. For the remaining 43 assets, λ_{implied} grows systematically with q across nearly all assets, consistent with the quadratic scaling in Eq. (31) at moderate moment orders. Defensive consumer staples such as COST, PEP, and PG record the lowest non-zero values at $q = 200$ ($\lambda_{\text{implied}} < 25$), while high-volatility assets such as ETH-USD (297.82), NFLX (914.06), and TSLA (653.04) record the highest. AMD records negative λ_{implied} at $q \geq 150$ (-221.07 and -517.30 respectively), indicating that the path’s space-filling capacity collapses faster than the cumulant diffusion can sustain—a regime with no direct counterpart in the original Gaspard framework and a marker of extreme finite-sample sensitivity in the return distribution.

Table 6 reveals that λ_{implied} declines sharply with horizon t across nearly all assets, falling from large values at $t = 1$ day and plateauing or zeroing out well before $t = 120$ days for the majority of the universe. The decay is most dramatic in the highest-volatility assets: NFLX falls from 696.10 at $t = 1$ to 12.15 at $t = 60$ and zeros out entirely by $t = 120$, while TSLA declines from 628.03 at $t = 1$ to 6.36 at $t = 120$, the only technology stock to retain a non-zero value at that horizon alongside INTC (1.12) and NVDA (1.45). ETH-USD and BTC-USD also maintain non-zero values up to $t = 120$ (2.94 and 1.18), reflecting the strong tail structure in these two assets. For financials, all assets reach their floor level by $t = 120$, but some, such as JPM, BAC, MS, C, and WFC, begin moving towards zero much earlier ($t = 40$ – 60), which is due to the progressively decreasing contribution of higher order cumulants as the effect of the central limit theorem takes effect. As for defensive and consumer staples sectors, their decay is the most drastic, with both KO and WMT already reaching zero by $t = 10$. The other two assets—PEP and PG—also reach zero by $t = 20$. AMD also maintains negative implied value throughout all investment periods ($\lambda_{\text{implied}} = -586.87$ to -5.15), which confirms that the collapse of D_{box} below unity at large moment orders is a structural feature of the return distribution rather than a short-horizon artefact.

Table 5: Implied dynamical ratio λ_{implied} (mean across all horizons t) by moment order q for all assets. Values at $q = 1$ are omitted as $D_{\text{box}} - 1 \approx 0$ renders the ratio numerically unstable. Negative entries indicate $D_{\text{box}} < 1$ at that moment order. Zero entries indicate $D_k \approx 0$ across all horizons, consistent with $\bar{\Gamma} = 0$ in Table 3.

Ticker	$q = 10$	$q = 50$	$q = 75$	$q = 100$	$q = 150$	$q = 200$
<i>Large Cap Technology</i>						
AAPL	1.27	6.00	9.53	13.32	22.94	30.40
MSFT	2.29	7.79	11.61	16.15	26.08	35.27
GOOG	0	0	0	0	0	0
AMZN	1.41	6.47	9.97	14.34	23.52	57.96
NVDA	1.37	5.94	10.01	12.89	27.96	111.77

Ticker	$q = 10$	$q = 50$	$q = 75$	$q = 100$	$q = 150$	$q = 200$
META	1.17	5.84	9.15	11.92	21.83	76.79
TSLA	1.39	7.26	11.25	17.92	47.98	653.04
NFLX	0.99	5.87	8.67	12.17	30.37	914.06
AMD	1.28	6.01	9.21	13.87	-221.07	-517.30
INTC	1.47	6.25	9.62	14.00	22.10	37.63
<i>Financials</i>						
JPM	1.57	5.70	8.79	12.48	19.63	28.18
BAC	1.41	5.97	9.32	12.84	19.04	33.88
GS	1.31	5.11	7.88	10.38	17.78	34.61
MS	1.25	6.14	10.55	14.11	22.87	38.43
WFC	1.41	5.34	8.51	11.79	17.46	27.27
BLK	1.54	6.63	10.06	14.67	21.25	34.15
C	1.41	6.36	10.19	13.77	22.32	34.67
AXP	1.38	5.73	8.75	11.65	19.63	30.72
V	2.57	9.60	15.74	22.45	36.38	59.50
MA	1.75	8.57	12.99	18.82	31.94	49.11
<i>Healthcare & Consumer</i>						
JNJ	0	0	0	0	0	0
PFE	0	0	0	0	0	0
UNH	1.41	5.36	8.18	11.12	19.00	27.81
MRK	2.95	6.71	9.63	14.06	20.47	28.53
ABBV	2.86	9.03	14.34	19.00	32.97	48.86
PG	2.46	4.91	7.37	10.29	15.39	21.18
KO	5.53	14.63	25.21	35.19	51.97	65.28
PEP	2.13	5.39	7.04	10.74	15.54	19.98
WMT	4.04	14.40	21.31	29.63	45.47	61.03
COST	0.53	1.55	2.52	3.26	5.21	7.32
<i>Energy & Industrials</i>						
XOM	1.67	6.28	9.66	12.70	20.30	29.35
CVX	1.83	5.48	8.83	11.83	19.51	32.12
COP	1.25	5.15	7.90	10.50	18.58	38.06
BA	1.50	6.69	10.63	15.60	25.95	45.34
CAT	0	0	0	0	0	0
GE	1.80	6.93	10.75	15.06	24.22	41.22
HON	1.85	6.25	9.92	13.00	20.11	30.64
LMT	1.73	6.08	9.35	13.72	21.99	31.57

Ticker	$q = 10$	$q = 50$	$q = 75$	$q = 100$	$q = 150$	$q = 200$
RTX	1.97	6.32	10.08	13.12	21.90	29.45
UPS	1.81	7.99	12.23	16.46	26.77	38.25
<i>Commodities & Crypto</i>						
GC=F	0	0	0	0	0	0
SI=F	0	0	0	0	0	0
CL=F	2.67	11.87	19.37	27.93	64.38	209.29
BTC-USD	1.31	9.52	15.55	20.69	44.03	86.80
ETH-USD	1.48	8.16	13.96	26.16	81.73	297.82
<i>International ETFs</i>						
EWJ	0	0	0	0	0	0
EWZ	1.37	5.33	8.15	10.95	21.17	63.33
FXI	2.12	5.47	7.95	10.84	17.67	25.84
EWG	4.39	13.92	22.20	29.94	52.13	71.51
EWU	3.44	8.01	11.98	17.84	29.67	42.61

Table 6: Implied dynamical ratio λ_{implied} (mean across all q) by horizon t for all assets. The sharp decline between $t = 40$ and $t = 60$ days reflects progressive suppression of higher-order cumulant contributions as the central limit effect sets in. Zero entries indicate $D_k \approx 0$ at all horizons.

Ticker	$t = 1$	$t = 10$	$t = 20$	$t = 40$	$t = 60$	$t = 120$
<i>Large Cap Technology</i>						
AAPL	55.28	7.91	3.85	1.90	1.30	0.00
MSFT	44.29	4.11	0.00	1.20	0.00	0.00
GOOG	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
AMZN	69.10	6.77	3.27	1.69	0.00	0.00
NVDA	145.39	13.38	5.78	2.69	1.93	1.45
META	89.82	9.23	5.06	2.70	1.80	0.00
TSLA	628.03	65.43	27.81	16.55	9.14	6.36
NFLX	696.10	70.34	35.67	17.97	12.15	0.00
AMD	-586.87	-59.26	-30.55	-14.75	-10.40	-5.15
INTC	73.47	7.78	3.81	2.48	2.16	1.12
<i>Financials</i>						
JPM	55.80	5.15	2.59	1.40	1.05	0.00
BAC	59.13	5.59	2.85	1.58	1.14	0.00
GS	47.04	4.51	2.31	1.34	0.00	0.00

Ticker	$t = 1$	$t = 10$	$t = 20$	$t = 40$	$t = 60$	$t = 120$
MS	66.89	6.44	3.28	1.87	1.52	0.00
WFC	52.70	4.72	2.37	1.29	1.08	0.00
BLK	43.08	3.95	0.00	1.22	0.00	0.00
C	63.31	6.51	3.18	1.60	1.18	0.00
AXP	55.81	5.41	2.75	1.52	1.15	0.00
V	44.70	4.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MA	55.44	3.62	2.52	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Healthcare & Consumer</i>						
JNJ	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
PFE	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
UNH	50.71	5.20	2.54	1.54	1.24	0.00
MRK	35.87	3.54	1.77	0.00	0.00	0.00
ABBV	38.38	3.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
PG	30.26	3.08	1.61	0.00	0.00	0.00
KO	32.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
PEP	31.44	2.79	1.62	0.00	0.00	0.00
WMT	29.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
COST	0.00	3.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Energy & Industrials</i>						
XOM	24.31	2.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CVX	48.56	4.40	2.49	1.51	0.00	0.00
COP	56.07	6.60	3.30	1.68	1.38	0.00
BA	72.96	8.20	4.33	2.09	1.57	0.00
CAT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
GE	53.01	4.16	2.32	0.00	0.00	0.00
HON	38.41	4.47	2.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
LMT	46.14	4.73	3.48	1.81	0.00	0.00
RTX	41.43	4.11	2.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
UPS	51.05	4.83	2.60	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Commodities & Crypto</i>						
GC=F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SI=F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CL=F	93.57	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
BTC-USD	150.52	14.01	7.06	3.43	2.45	1.18
ETH-USD	354.36	35.88	15.40	8.68	5.88	2.94
<i>International ETFs</i>						

Ticker	$t = 1$	$t = 10$	$t = 20$	$t = 40$	$t = 60$	$t = 120$
EWJ	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EWZ	82.01	7.30	3.81	1.92	1.32	0.00
FXI	41.19	4.40	2.06	1.08	0.00	0.00
EWG	32.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EWU	34.07	3.77	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6 Conclusion

The present paper presents extensive evidence of robust multifractal nature of financial markets using a heterogenous sample of 50 assets belonging to six different economic sectors. Non-linearity of the function $\tau(q)$, presence of concave singularity spectra $f(\alpha)$ and divergence of fluctuation functions in terms of moment order all serve to indicate that the returns process cannot be captured using monofractals or Gaussian models. Instead, the returns show structural heterogeneous scaling and long memory properties which are common to all asset classes used in the analysis. From the perspective of finance, these results imply that any model based solely on variance, such as mean-variance portfolio optimization and VaR under the assumption of Gaussianity, would consistently underestimate the likelihood and scale of extreme losses.

The cross-industry analysis shows clear diversity in $\Delta\alpha$, suggesting that the existence of multifractality cannot be attributed to any industry. Consumer staples and defensive stocks such as KO, PEP, and JNJ show unexpectedly large spectral widths, indicating that the constant demand associated with those stocks does not preclude intermittent shocks and volatility memory effects. This observation has practical applications to portfolio management insofar as stocks that were chosen as safe investments on the basis of low volatility might conceal structural non-linearity and become exposed to correlated drawdowns during extreme events unobservable to traditional statistical measures of volatility. Energy and industrial sector stocks maintain high $\Delta\alpha$, which corresponds to their vulnerability to exogenous shocks such as sudden changes in commodity markets and international affairs. Technology stocks show intermediate levels of multifractality, as expected due to superior liquidity, but still exhibit significant spectral widths, suggesting that even highly liquid markets demonstrate persistent non-linear dependence incompatible with the efficient market hypothesis in the strong form.

The symmetric fluctuation analysis reveals a gradual decrease in the Pearson correlation coefficient between $F_{+q}(s)$ and $F_{-q}(s)$ as $|q|$ grows, with the steepest decreases seen in KO, PEP, JNJ, CVX, and CL=F, with PEP having the lowest coefficient $\rho = -0.1332$. The asymmetry in the scaling of large positive vs large negative tail fluctuations can be

easily explained in terms of financial theory: this implies that the dynamics of crashes and rallies do not mirror one another, and that there are separate statistical models that govern the occurrence of downside vs upside tail events of similar size. This aligns with the empirical results of the leverage effect: negative return shocks are much stronger catalysts for volatility than positive shocks, lending support to the choice of asymmetric risk metrics, like the Expected Shortfall, against symmetric ones. Instruments in the financial industry, such as MA, BLK, AXP, and GS, show particularly strong correlations in their large fluctuations, likely due to the nature of balance sheet constraints and systemic risks. Technology stocks like AAPL, MSFT, GOOG, and AMZN tend to retain relatively high correlation floors at large $|q|$.

The drawdowns of all studied assets show deviations from the patterns implied by the independence and identical distribution of returns, indicating the impact of regime-dependent pricing behavior and the clustering of extreme drawdowns, which cannot be explained by the return-based models. In terms of financial implications, it means that the risk models assuming independence between sequential daily losses will underestimate both duration and magnitude of drawdowns. Moreover, coordinated moves of the correlated assets during drawdown periods will add even more systemic risk, because diversification effect fails at the times when it is really needed. It is especially relevant to leveraged strategies and derivatives portfolios, since margin calls and leverage reduction lead to contagion among the positions, as demonstrated during the 2008–2009 crisis and the March 2020 liquidity crunch.

The cumulant-based characteristic function analysis finds that out of 50 assets, 43 have practically significant non-stationarity of $D_k(t)$ in at least one backtested window; these assets tend to display such violations overwhelmingly at short horizons $t \leq 20$. The financial services industry leads the cross-sectional distribution of $\bar{\Gamma}$, with the largest $\bar{\Gamma}$ recorded by Citigroup, Morgan Stanley, and Bank of America; this reflects the lasting impact on the tails of the non-Gaussian distribution induced by the 2008-2009 financial crisis. From a regulatory point of view, the presence of leptokurtic violations at shorter horizons becomes especially important for firms with daily trading activities since risk measurements using internal models calibrated at longer horizons will underestimate tail risk precisely at the times when margin requirements are binding. Moreover, the window dependence of Γ implies that any calibration using backtested risk measures based on tranquil windows will lead to an unrealistically optimistic assessment of risk.

Box-counting fractal analysis of the characteristic function path $\Phi(t; q)$ gives us another geometric view of return complexity. Parabola-like growth of $D_{\text{box}}(q) - 1$ as a function of the moment order q at intermediate frequencies is consistent with the quadratic scaling behavior predicted by the relation between the fractal excess in hydrodynamic modes and the ratio of the diffusion coefficient to the Lyapunov exponent for chaotic diffusions. In

the financial application, the dynamical ratio λ_{implied} may be seen as the ratio of speed of diffusion of information relevant to price to the speed of response of prices to initial information; the higher the ratio, the more price processes become diffusive rather than deterministic. However, the non-monotonicity of behaviour seen in high volatility financial instruments like ETH-USD, AMD, and CL=F, along with the pathological value of negative λ_{implied} found for AMD at higher orders of moment, suggests there may be certain structural weaknesses in the underlying return distribution for these financial assets which traditional risk measures cannot identify. The observation of horizon-resolved decline in λ_{implied} shows that the deviation from Gaussian cumulant expansion is most significant at shorter horizons, before dissipating as the central limit theorem takes effect. This deviation is found to persist up to much longer horizons for cryptocurrencies and volatile equities.

Together, the above observations suggest that financial markets are complex adaptive systems that possess scale-dependent non-linear dynamics that cannot be described using the conventional assumption of homogeneous scaling. The use of multifractals along with symmetric fluctuation analysis, drawdown analysis, cumulant scaling of the characteristic function, and geometric scaling with the help of box counting provides a much more elaborate description of financial markets that would have practical applications for the modeling of market volatility, the estimation of tail risks, portfolio constructions, and stress testing scenarios under both normal and stressed market regimes. Possible directions for further research could include incorporating $\Delta\alpha$ and $\bar{\Gamma}$ as measures of risk and using the ratio D/λ as an indicator of market fragility based on intraday returns.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge support provided by the Department of Information Technology at K. J. Somaiya School of Engineering, Somaiya Vidyavihar University. The authors declare no conflicts of interest. No external funding was received. During preparation of this work the authors used Claude by Anthropic for formatting and language polishing; all content was reviewed and edited by the authors.

References

- [1] Louis Bachelier. *Théorie de la Spéculation*. PhD thesis, University of Paris, 1900.
- [2] Eugene F. Fama. Efficient capital markets: A review of theory and empirical work. *Journal of Finance*, 25(2):383–423, 1970.

- [3] Eugene F. Fama. Efficient capital markets: II. *Journal of Finance*, 46(5):1575–1617, 1991.
- [4] M. F. M. Osborne. Brownian motion in the stock market. *Operations Research*, 7(2):145–173, 1959.
- [5] Benoit B. Mandelbrot. The variation of certain speculative prices. *Journal of Business*, 36(4):394–419, 1963.
- [6] Parameswaran Gopikrishnan, Vasiliki Plerou, Luís A. N. Amaral, Martin Meyer, and H. Eugene Stanley. Scaling of the distribution of fluctuations of financial market indices. *Physical Review E*, 60(5):5305–5316, 1999.
- [7] Vasiliki Plerou, Parameswaran Gopikrishnan, Luís A. N. Amaral, Martin Meyer, and H. Eugene Stanley. Scaling of the distribution of price fluctuations of individual companies. *Physical Review E*, 60(6):6519–6529, 1999.
- [8] Robert F. Engle. Autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity with estimates of the variance of United Kingdom inflation. *Econometrica*, 50(4):987–1008, 1982.
- [9] Tim Bollerslev. Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity. *Journal of Econometrics*, 31(3):307–327, 1986.
- [10] Rama Cont. Empirical properties of asset returns: Stylized facts and statistical issues. *Quantitative Finance*, 1(2):223–236, 2001.
- [11] Jean-Philippe Bouchaud, Andrew Matacz, and Marc Potters. Leverage effect in financial markets: The retarded volatility model. *Physical Review Letters*, 87:228701, 2001.
- [12] Rosario N. Mantegna and H. Eugene Stanley. *An Introduction to Econophysics: Correlations and Complexity in Finance*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2000.
- [13] Sudhir Ranjan Jain. Fractal-like quasienergy spectrum in the Fermi-Ulam model. *Physical Review Letters*, 70:3553, 1993.
- [14] Sudhir Ranjan Jain and Arun Kumar Pati. Adiabatic geometric phases and response functions. *Physical Review Letters*, 80:650, 1998.
- [15] Sudhir Ranjan Jain and Pierre Gaspard. Dynamical response and time correlation functions in random quantum systems. *Annals of Physics*, 474:169922, 2025.
- [16] Zhi-Qiang Jiang, Wen-Jie Xie, Wei-Xing Zhou, and Didier Sornette. Multifractal analysis of financial markets: A review. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 82(12):125901, 2019.

- [17] Thomas C. Halsey, Mogens H. Jensen, Leo P. Kadanoff, Itamar Procaccia, and Boris I. Shraiman. Fractal measures and their singularities: The characterization of strange sets. *Physical Review A*, 33(2):1141–1151, 1986.
- [18] Uriel Frisch and Giorgio Parisi. On the singularity structure of fully developed turbulence. In M. Gil, R. Benzi, and G. Parisi, editors, *Turbulence and Predictability in Geophysical Fluid Dynamics and Climate Dynamics*, pages 84–88. Elsevier, 1985.
- [19] T. Di Matteo. Multi-scaling in finance. *Quantitative Finance*, 7(1):21–36, 2007.
- [20] Benoit B. Mandelbrot. Intermittent turbulence in self-similar cascades: Divergence of high moments and dimension of the carrier. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 62(2):331–358, 1974.
- [21] S. Ghashghaie, W. Breymann, J. Peinke, P. Talkner, and Y. Dodge. Turbulent cascades in foreign exchange markets. *Nature*, 381(6585):767–770, 1996.
- [22] Rosario N. Mantegna and H. Eugene Stanley. Scaling behaviour in the dynamics of an economic index. *Nature*, 376(6535):46–49, 1995.
- [23] Rosario N. Mantegna and H. Eugene Stanley. Turbulence and financial markets. *Nature*, 383(6601):587–588, 1996.
- [24] Benoit B. Mandelbrot, Adlai J. Fisher, and Laurent E. Calvet. A multifractal model of asset returns. Discussion Paper 1164, Cowles Foundation for Research in Economics, Yale University, 1997.
- [25] Laurent Calvet and Adlai Fisher. Forecasting multifractal volatility. *Journal of Econometrics*, 105(1):27–58, 2001.
- [26] Laurent Calvet and Adlai Fisher. How to forecast long-run volatility: Regime switching and the estimation of multifractal processes. *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, 2:49–83, 2004.
- [27] Thomas Lux. The Markov-switching multifractal model of asset returns: GMM estimation and linear forecasting of volatility. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 26(2):194–210, 2008.
- [28] Jan W. Kantelhardt, Stephan A. Zschiegner, Eva Koscielny-Bunde, Shlomo Havlin, Armin Bunde, and H. Eugene Stanley. Multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis of nonstationary time series. *Physica A*, 316(1–4):87–114, 2002.
- [29] C.-K. Peng, Sergey V. Buldyrev, Shlomo Havlin, M. Simons, H. Eugene Stanley, and Ary L. Goldberger. Mosaic organization of DNA nucleotides. *Physical Review E*, 49(2):1685–1689, 1994.

- [30] Dusan Stosic, Darko Stosic, Tatijana Stosic, and H. Eugene Stanley. Multifractal properties of price change and volume change of stock market indices. *Physica A*, 428:46–51, 2015.
- [31] Syed Aun R. Rizvi, Ginanjar Dewandaru, Obiyathulla I. Bacha, and Mansur Masih. An analysis of stock market efficiency: Developed vs Islamic stock markets using MF-DFA. *Physica A*, 407:86–99, 2014.
- [32] Luciano Zunino, Benjamin M. Tabak, Alejandra Figliola, Darío G. Pérez, Mario Garavaglia, and Osvaldo A. Rosso. A multifractal approach for stock market inefficiency. *Physica A*, 387(26):6558–6566, 2008.
- [33] Ladislav Kristoufek and Miloslav Vosvrda. Measuring capital market efficiency: Global and local correlations structure. *Physica A*, 392(1):184–193, 2013.
- [34] T. Di Matteo, T. Aste, and M. M. Dacorogna. Long-term memories of developed and emerging markets: Using the scaling analysis to characterize their stage of development. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(4):827–851, 2005.
- [35] Jose Alvarez-Ramirez, Eduardo Rodriguez, and Juan Carlos Echeverria. A DFA approach for assessing asymmetric correlations. *Physica A*, 388(12):2263–2270, 2009.
- [36] Guangxi Cao, Jie Cao, and Longbing Xu. Asymmetric multifractal scaling behavior in the Chinese stock market: Based on asymmetric MF-DFA. *Physica A*, 392(4):797–807, 2013.
- [37] Paweł Oświecimka, Jarosław Kwapien, and Stanisław Drożdż. Wavelet versus detrended fluctuation analysis of multifractal structures. *Physical Review E*, 74(1):016103, 2006.
- [38] Didier Sornette. *Why Stock Markets Crash: Critical Events in Complex Financial Systems*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, 2003.
- [39] Benoit B. Mandelbrot. Multifractal measures, especially for the geophysicist. *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, 131(1–2):5–42, 1989.
- [40] Wei-Xing Zhou. Finite-size effect and the components of multifractality in financial volatility. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 45(2):147–155, 2012.
- [41] Ashvin B. Chhabra and Roderick V. Jensen. Direct determination of the $f(\alpha)$ singularity spectrum. *Physical Review Letters*, 62(12):1327–1330, 1989.
- [42] Alfréd Rényi. On measures of information and entropy. In *Proceedings of the 4th Berkeley Symposium on Mathematics, Statistics and Probability*, volume 1, pages 547–561. University of California Press, 1961.

- [43] Peter Grassberger. Generalized dimensions of strange attractors. *Physics Letters A*, 97(6):227–230, 1983.
- [44] H. G. E. Hentschel and Itamar Procaccia. The infinite number of generalized dimensions of fractals and strange attractors. *Physica D*, 8(3):435–444, 1983.
- [45] Raffaello Morales, T. Di Matteo, Ruggero Gramatica, and Tomaso Aste. Dynamical generalized Hurst exponent as a tool to monitor unstable periods in financial time series. *Physica A*, 391(11):3180–3189, 2012.
- [46] Rongbao Gu, Yanmin Shao, and Qingnan Wang. Is the efficiency of stock market correlated with multifractality? Evidence from the Shanghai stock market. *Physica A*, 392(2):361–370, 2013.
- [47] Andrew W. Lo. The adaptive markets hypothesis. *Journal of Portfolio Management*, 30(5):15–29, 2004.
- [48] James Theiler, Stephen Eubank, André Longtin, Bryan Galdrikian, and J. Doynne Farmer. Testing for nonlinearity in time series: The method of surrogate data. *Physica D*, 58:77–94, 1992.
- [49] Thomas Schreiber and Andreas Schmitz. Improved surrogate data for nonlinearity tests. *Physical Review Letters*, 77(4):635–638, 1996.
- [50] Wei-Xing Zhou. The components of empirical multifractality in financial returns. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 88(2):28004, 2009.
- [51] Paweł Oświecimka, Jarosław Kwapien, Stanisław Drożdż, Andrzej Z. Górski, and Rafał Rak. Different fractal properties of positive and negative returns. *Acta Physica Polonica A*, 114(3):547–553, 2008.
- [52] Kun Hu, Plamen Ch. Ivanov, Zhi Chen, Pedro Carpena, and H. Eugene Stanley. Effect of trends on detrended fluctuation analysis. *Physical Review E*, 64(1):011114, 2001.
- [53] Ying-Hui Shao, Gao-Feng Gu, Zhi-Qiang Jiang, Wei-Xing Zhou, and Didier Sornette. Comparing the performance of FA, DFA and DMA using different synthetic long-range correlated time series. *Scientific Reports*, 2:835, 2012.
- [54] Dariusz Grech and Zygmunt Mazur. On the scaling ranges of detrended fluctuation analysis for long-term memory correlated short series of data. *Physica A*, 392(10):2384–2397, 2013.
- [55] Shanshan He and Yudong Wang. Revisiting the multifractality in stock returns and its modeling implications. *Physica A*, 467:11–20, 2017.

- [56] Kaushik Matia, Yosef Ashkenazy, and H. Eugene Stanley. Multifractal properties of price fluctuations of stock and commodities. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 61(3): 422–428, 2003.
- [57] Zoltán Eisler and János Kertész. Multifractal model of asset returns with leverage effect. *Physica A*, 343:603–622, 2004.
- [58] Bertrand Pochart and Jean-Philippe Bouchaud. The skewed multifractal random walk with applications to option smiles. *Quantitative Finance*, 2:303–314, 2002.
- [59] Jarosław Kwapien and Stanisław Drożdż. Physical approach to complex systems. *Physics Reports*, 515(3–4):115–226, 2012.
- [60] Stanisław Drożdż, Jarosław Kwapien, Paweł Oświecimka, and Rafał Rak. The foreign exchange market: Return distributions, multifractality, anomalous multifractality and the Epps effect. *New Journal of Physics*, 12(10):105003, 2010.
- [61] Kian-Ping Lim and Robert Brooks. The evolution of stock market efficiency over time: A survey of the empirical literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 25(1): 69–108, 2011.
- [62] Da Xu and Christian Beck. Symbolic dynamics techniques for complex systems: Application to share price dynamics. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 118(3):30001, 2017.
- [63] Kenneth J. Falconer. *Fractal Geometry: Mathematical Foundations and Applications*. Wiley, Chichester, 1990.
- [64] Benoit B. Mandelbrot. *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*. W.H. Freeman, New York, 1983.
- [65] Aurelio F. Bariviera, María José Basgall, Waldo Hasperúe, and Marcelo Naiouf. Some stylized facts of the Bitcoin market. *Physica A*, 484:82–90, 2017.
- [66] Stanisław Drożdż, Jarosław Kwapien, Paweł Oświecimka, Tomasz Stanisł, and Marcin Wątarek. Complexity in economic and social systems: Cryptocurrency market at around COVID-19. *Entropy*, 22(9):1043, 2020.
- [67] Aviral Kumar Tiwari, Claudiu Tiberiu Albulescu, and Seong-Min Yoon. A multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis of financial market efficiency: Comparison using Dow Jones sector ETF indices. *Physica A*, 483:182–192, 2017.
- [68] Pierre Gaspard, Isabelle Claus, Thomas Gilbert, and J. Robert Dorfman. The fractality of the hydrodynamic modes of diffusion. *Physical Review Letters*, 86:1506, 2000.